

Cognitive Screening In Acute Stroke Patients At Zainoel Abidin Hospital Banda Aceh

Ika Marlia¹, Suherman²

^{1,2} Department of Neurology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Syiah Kuala / Zainoel Abidin Hospital Banda Aceh

Email: ikamarlia@gmail.com

Abstract:

Introduction: Current literature suggests that two-thirds of patients will have cognitive impairment at 3 months post-stroke. There is no 'gold standard' cognitive screening tool. Several literature have compared the difference in quality between the Montreal cognitive assesment (MoCA) and the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) for screening post-stroke. This study aimed to cognitive screening in acute stroke.

Methods :The descriptive observational study with cross-sectional method was conducted in January-March 2019. The research was held at neurology ward in Zainoel Abidin Hospital Banda Aceh. A convenience sample of 52 patients, admitted with stroke was examined through brain CT scan to characterize strokes by its type (ischemic or hemorrhagic) and using the MMSE and the Indonesia version of MoCA (MoCA-Ina) to screening cognitive function.

Results :Stroke most common in middle age (80.8%) and ischemic stroke higher than hemorrhagic. Cognitive impairment were more commonly in acute stroke. Cognitive function with MoCA-Ina most frequent moderate cognitive impairment (48.1%) and probable cognitive impairment (40.4%) by MMSE, with memory domain (94.2%). MoCA is more sensitive than MMSE in mild cognitive impairment.

Conclusion :Cognitive screening more important in acute stroke and MoCA is superior to MMSE for the detection of vascular cognitive impairment in acute stroke.

Keywords:

Stroke, cognitive impairment, MMSE, MoCA version Indonesia

Tetanus: Review Of A Case Series

Nur Astini¹, Deri Rivano¹, Nurul Fajri¹, Nona Suci Rahayu¹

¹Department of Neurology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Dr. Zainoel Abidin General Hospital, Banda Aceh, Indonesia

Email: astinisyiful@gmail.com

Abstract:

Background: Generalized tetanus is the most common diagnosis when patients initially experiencing spasm of the masseter muscle or trismus. The principles of treating tetanus are reducing muscle spasms, rigidity and autonomic instability, neutralization of tetanus toxin with HTIG, wound debridement and antibiotics to eradicate proliferating bacteria at the wound site.

Methods: We reviewed cases series selected from patients attending to our department. Observational descriptive study of patient's medical records.

Results: We observed 3 cases

Case 1: Male 60 years with fatigue throughout the limbs and abdominal wall experienced by patients since 1 day before admission to the hospital. The source was from wound at the left thigh. Epithotonus, abdominal wall muscular defans and seizures provoked by sound. During treatment, general condition more stable and discharge home on the 20th day of the treatment.

Case 2 : Female 60 years with a main complaint was stiffness around the mouth since 2 days before admission to the hospital. Epithotonus, abdominal wall muscular defans and seizures provoked by sound. Home care on the 10th day of treatment.

Case 3: Male 58 years old with generalized seizure, duration of 20-30 seconds, difficulty of swallowing, and stiffness in the patient's mouth since 3 days before admission to the hospital. Trismus and stiffness obtained on limb muscles. Patient had improvement on the general condition and the seizure was resolved. Patient was discharged home on the 13th day of treatment.

All patients received 500 IU IM TIG therapy, intravenous Ceftriaxone 1 g/12 hours, intravenous Metronidazole 500 mg/8 hours and intravenous Diazepam.

Conclusions: This is a review of a case series, our data has shown that tetanus when its handled in accordance with the Guidelines will provide a good prognosis. We recommend that the tetanus immunization program in developing countries run successfully, to reduce the incidence and the death rate of tetanus.

Key Words:

Tetanus, TIG, case series, developing countries, epithotonus, abdominal wall muscular defans, trismus

Developing composite molecular system network of aggression

Anila Khalique

State Key Laboratory of Medicinal Chemical Biology, Key Laboratory of Bioactive Materials of Ministry of Education, College of Life Science, Nankai University, Tianjin, PR China.

Email: anila.khalique@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Objective: It is now widely established that aggressive behavior is underpinned by several genetic and molecular factors. Here we use the approaches of systems biology in order to illustrate the composite molecular network which delineates the molecular events that forms the underlying molecular basis of anger development and its progression.

Methodology: Briefly, molecular network of each aggression associated gene (n=25) will be explored by text mining, co-expression, co-localization, physical and/or transcriptional interactions using STRING v9.0. Attempts were made in order to link one molecular network with other at variety of confidence levels. Gradient sieving of the confidence filters start with 0.9, followed by 0.7 and 0.4. Finally, the lacunae left in the interactions will be filled using basic physiology of the genes and/or encoded proteins.

Results: NGF and BDNF proteins showed maximum number of intermediate binding partners, which through their intermediate partner, GIPC1, link with DRD2 receptor. DRD2 in turn associated with DRD3, DRD4 and SLC6A3. These interactions congregate them with the physiology of dopamine and other proteins involved in cAMP regulation like HTR1B, AKAP5, OXT, AVP and MAOA. Of these SLC6A3, HTR1B and MAOA form a molecular bridge between dopamine and serotonin physiology. The later involve additional proteins like SLC6A4, TPH1 and TPH2. An auxiliary association was also noted between SLC6A3 with AR which in turn result in the transcriptional regulation via CREB, reflecting the role of testosterone with the anger physiology. Finally the CREB is known to regulate the expression of BDNF making the entire molecular network link together.

Conclusion: The study provide a molecular resolution to the aggression physiology which could be exploited to screen the targeted population and design therapeutic interventions.

Effectiveness of the Schema Therapy on Executive Functions of Chronic Depression Disorder

Dr. Anita Azarkolah

Assistant Professor of Psychiatry, School of Medicine and Allied Medical Sciences, Fatemi Hospital, Ardabil
University of Medical Sciences, Iran

Email: dra.azarkolah@gmail.com

Abstract:

Regarding the prevalence of depression and specially chronic depression in communities during recent years and the resistance that patients have shown to the treatment approaches, it seemed essential to focus more attention on this disorder. The objective of this research is evaluation to effectiveness of the schema therapy on executive functions of chronic depression disorder. To start the research, 8 patients from Medical Center in 13 District in Tehran city, 4 men and 4 women, who were diagnosed with chronic depression were selected. These patients were assessed using Beck Depression Questionnaires and Wisconsin Cards. The results showed for the 8 cases, there has been a decrease in wrong answers relating Wisconsin Cards within the treatment sessions. These results have important implications for the treatment and pathology of these patients.

Key Words:

Schema therapy, chronic depression, Executive functions

Role Type 3 Diabetes Mellitus In The Management Neurological And Psychiatric Disorders, Pre And Post-Operative Care Of Neuro Surgeries, During The Administration Of General Anaesthesia For All The Surgeries, Gestation Period And the General Health Of Neonates, Infants, And Toddlers And The Management Of Type 3 Diabetes Mellitus

N. Gattupalli,^{1,2,*} B. Gouri Sankara Krishna^{1,2}

¹ University Name, Rajeev Gandhi University of Health Sciences Bangalore, Karnataka, India

² State University of Campinas, Sharavathi Dental College Shivamogga, Karnataka, India

³ Shree Narayana Datta Dental Clinic Kandukur Prakasm District, Andhra Pradesh, India

Email: gattgoushankrish@gmail.com

Abstract:

Insulin is the hormone which cannot pass through the blood brain barrier. To compensate the insulin demand, brain produces its own insulin and the insulin producing cells of the brain are called as Dileep 2, 3, and 5 cells which are situated at the serotonin receptors of cerebral cortex of brain the reduced function of these Dileep cells is called Type 3 Diabetes Mellitus in other hand it is also called as Brain Diabetes. Previously it is considered as the synonyme of Alzimers Disease and after a lot of studies it was considered it was considered as a separate entity. And a lot of role in the management neurological and Psychiatric disorders, pre and post-operative care of Neuro surgeries, during the administration of general anaesthesia for all the Surgeries, gestation period and the general health of Neonates, Infants, and toddlers that is why the management of Type 3 Diabetes is having a lot of significance in the medical field. The reason is if any improper ATP generation of the brain causes the Brain fatigue thick is generally characterized by insomnia and memory impairment. Especially during the induction of Non Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Stages 3 and 4 brain requires highest amount of Insulin. And during the treatment of Type 3 Diabetes the important key is the Insulin and Glucose levels of Cerebro Spinal Fluid the reason is the Cerebro Spinal Fluid is nothing but the lymphatic drainage of the brain and Spinal cord. The normal range of Insulin Of Cerebro Spinal Fluid is 3.22 to 4.77 pmol/L and the range of glucose of Cerebro Spinal Fluid is 2.5 and 4.5 mmol/L. through this key if the Insulin levels are high we can come to know that there is a well-established evidence of insulin resistancy and to treat this Metformin and Chromium are the best choice. And for the lower production of the insulin only the symptomatic treatment is the choice. Now without knowing this fact, now a days the doctors are just dumping sedatives and anty depressant drugs which mask NREM stage 3&4 and REM sleeps. That is why there is a lot of nesity to concentrate on this field.

Key Words:

Type 3 Diabetes mellitus is the ut most important area of the medicine which helps the doctor to pay attention in the much better way to study about a lot of role in the management neurological and Psychiatric disorders, pre and post-operative care of Neuro surgeries, during the administration of general anaesthesia for all the Surgeries, gestation period and the general health of Neonates, Infants, and toddlers that is why the management of Type 3 Diabetes is having a lot of significance in the medical field.

Figure 1: The insulin Production cells of brain situated near the serotonin receptors oot the cerebral cortex of the brain.

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3. Richerd Camp Bell
4. Alan D Raguso

Potential role of Serpina3n in neuroprotection after Ischemic stroke.

Mehwish Saba Aslam

Southeast University School of Medicine, Nanjing, China

Email: mehwishsaba19@outlook.com

Abstract:

Ischemic stroke is a ruinous CNS insult with finite effective therapeutical approaches. Primary limitation to develop novel restorative drugs is partially understood multidimensional underlying mechanisms and complicated crosstalk between them aiding to this pathophysiology. Recently, extracellular liberation of Granzyme B has been reported as an aider to neurodegeneration followed by CNS Ischemia. Inhibition of Granzyme B can be considered as one of the potential approach to reduce the neuronal damage. Murine serine protease inhibitor Serpina3n has a unique affinity for granzyme B while its human homolog serpina3 is incapable to inhibit granzyme B. By considering such reports, serpina3n can be considered as a potent therapeutical strategy to induce neuroprotection subsequent to ischemia by inhibiting granzyme B and serpina3 can be taken in parallel to investigate the underlying mechanism and unveil the contributing factors. Recombinant serpina3n and serpina3 proteins were overexpressed using mammalian cells and purified. Recombinant proteins were tested for their invitro granzyme B inhibition. Neuroprotective effects of both proteins at different concentrations 20mM, 50mM and 100mM were investigated with N2A cell line by using invitro enzymatic ischemia/reperfusion model. Furthermore invivo experiments were undertaken by generating photothrombic ischemic mouse model and treated with 50mg/kg of recombinant proteins. Harvested brains were used to evaluate the infarct volume, immunohistochemical tests and western blot analysis for treated and untreated groups. Treatment with recombinant serpina3n and serpina3 increased cell viability in dosage dependent manner invitro followed by enzymatic ischemia. Post-ischemia administration induced neuroprotection confirmed by infarction volume. Exogenous proteins were successfully delivered to the ischemic lesion site across the blood brain-barrier. Post- ischemia Serpina3n and Serpina3 induce neuroprotection and can be delivered successfully to the lesion focal area.

Key Words:

Ischemic stroke, therapeutical approaches, neurodegeneration, biomedical applications.

Malignant Pathology of Brain Meningioma Tumor as the Best Predictor for Mortality and Recurrency rate of Meningioma.

Dr. Mojtaba Mafi

M.D. Medical Doctor , Physician, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Iran

Email: mojtaba1981m@gmail.com

Abstract:

We studied on meningioma among 614 patients with Brain Tumor (consists of meningioma, glioma and pituitary Tumor). 145 patients had meningioma. Our results are in various topics: 1. Clinical features of meningioma 2. Anatomical distribution 3. Radiation induced meningioma 4. Meningioma and foster Kennedy syndrome 5. Meningioma and pseudo foster Kennedy syndrome 6. Multiple meningioma 7. Post traumatic and skull fracture meningioma 8. Cutaneous meningioma 9. Meningioma and DVT 10. Trigeminal neuralgia and meningioma 11. Recurrent meningioma 12. Meningioma mortality rate and some others. We are going on to continue this study. This research project has been held in neurosurgery ward Shariati Hospital and had been scientifically registered. We studied during 6 years on meningioma patients to find the risk factors for meningioma recurrence as well as answer to these questions: 1. what is the recurrence rate of meningioma? 2. Which anatomical locations are more prevalent for overall Recurrency? 3. What is Tumor specific recurrence rate according to anatomical location? 4. How long does it take after meningioma surgery till Tumor recurrence? 5. Are age and gender determining factors for meningioma recurrency? 6. The correlation between meningioma cellular pathology and recurrency? 7. Is mortality rate of recurrent meningioma more than primary Tumor? We found that 20.7% of all patients with meningioma recur after 4.6 years after surgery. Female to male ratio was 1.72 among recurrent tumours with no significant difference with this ratio among all meningioma study sample was 1.96 but it seems recurrence rate is more among men. The more prevalent anatomical location for overall recurrency were: 1. Convexity: 43.3% 2. Parasagittal: 26.7% 3. Sphenoid wing: 16.7% Tumor specific recurrence rate: 1. Parasagittal: 42% 2. Pentorial: 33.3 % 3. Convexity: 27.6% Tumor specific mortality rate: 1. C-P Angle: 33.3% 2. Petroclival: 25% 3. Sphenoid wing = Convexity: 16.7% Mortality rate among recurrent meningioma patients is 13.3% in compare with primary meningioma patients' mortality rate that was 6.9%, is approximately 2 times more. 75% of recurrent tumours with mortality were malignance meningioma pathologically or anaplastic meningioma, it shows that cellular malignance pathology has an important role for meningioma mortality and recurrency. We dedicate with honour the surgical procedures in details, follow up outcomes, history of radiotherapy and cellular pathology at oral presentation time. Thanks and regards. Mojtaba Mafi, MD, Study director. Fateme Rezvani, Bioinformatics, Study manager.

Taurine & Analogues in Aggressive Behavior and in its Alleviation

R C Gupta

SASRD Nagaland University, Medziphema, India

Email: rameshgupta1954@gmail.com

Abstract:

Aggression always has a motive to place the opponent in danger. It is a forceful, hostile or attacking behavior with an intention to cause harm or an act intended to increase relative social & individual dominance. Aggressive behaviors are often exhibited by individuals with psychiatric disorders, including substance abuse, personality disorders, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and anxiety disorders. Brain chemicals are said to be involve in regulation of such activities. Amino acids and amines in the central nervous system have been shown to play a critical role in aggressive behaviors. In particular, taurine, a sulfur-containing amino acid; chemically 2- Amino ethane sulfonic acid which acts as an inhibitory neuromodulator, has been found to be involved in aggressive behaviors. It is now almost establish that deficiency in this inhibitory modulator is associated with aggressive behaviors, a large number of evidences provides clue that taurine treatment reduces aggressive behaviors. In fact, a large body of direct or indirect experimental evidence supports the effectiveness of taurine and its analogues in suppressing aggressive behaviors are well documented. Particularly, within the perspective of natural pharmacotherapy, taurine-supplemented diets particularly; taurine containing functional food, nutraceuticals, designer foods are potentially helpful for reducing aggressive behaviors in patients with a wide variety of neuropsychiatric disorders. Amino acids have their own limitations, e.g., their restricted ability to cross the blood-brain barrier. Thus, pro-drugs and analogues, homologues, derivatives of taurine can constitute a novel class of effective agents for aggressive behaviors in patients with neuropsychiatric disorders.

Key Words:

Aggressive behavior; taurine; psychopharmacotherapy; aggression

Parkinsonism related to lipoma of brain: A Case Report

Sangmin Park¹, Eungseok Oh²

¹ Seoul National University Hospital, Department of Neurology, Seoul, Korea

² Chungnam National University Hospital, Department of Neurology, Daejeon, Korea

Email: samvaknin@gmail.com

Abstract:

Parkinsonism included many other conditions that showed parkinsonian symptoms regardless of the cause. We experienced patient who showed Parkinsonism related to lipoma of brain and no response to levodopa.

A 48-year-old man showed slowly progressive right hand tremor, gait disturbance and bradykinesia before 1 year ago. The major parkinsonian features were masked face, rigidity of both upper extremities, bradykinesia, gait disturbance and postural instability without falling tendency, but resting tremor was not shown. Initial United Parkinson Disease Rating Scales (UPDRS) part III score was 27. Gadolinium enhanced brain magnetic resonance image(MRI) showed abnormal heterogenous enhancement mass-like lesion on inferior free margin of falx cerebri with mild ventricular dilatation and vasogenic edema on periventricular area and both frontal subcortical white matter(Figure 1). Dopamine transporter scans showed decreased uptake in both caudate nucleus and both dorsal posterior putamen (right>left) (Figure 2). He was suspected lipoma with dysgenesis of corpus callosum and transferred other hospital for surgery. He was treated with Levodopa (900mg) more than 4 month, but Parkinsonism was not improved. But 9 months after surgery, Parkinsonism was mild improved and UPDRS part III score was 14.

In this case, brain MRI should be used to differential diagnosis of idiopathic Parkinson disease and secondary Parkinson disease, as well relative young age onset.

Key Words:

Parkinsonism, lipoma, vasogenic edema, magnetic resonance image, dopamine transporter scan, neurology

Figure 1: Preoperative brain MRI showed abnormal heterogenous enhancement mass-like lesion on inferior free margin of falx cerebri with mild ventricular dilatation and vasogenic edema on periventricular area and both frontal subcortical white matter.

Figure 2: Dopamine transporter PET showed decreased uptake in both caudate nucleus and both dorsal posterior putamen (right>left).

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Direct evidence of viral infection and mitochondrial alterations in the brain of fetuses at high risk for schizophrenia

Dr. Segundo Mesa Castillo

Psychiatric Hospital of Havana, CA 10800, Cuba

Email: segundo@infomed.sld.cu

Abstract:

There is increasing evidences that favor the prenatal beginning of schizophrenia. These evidences point toward intra-uterine environmental factors that act specifically during the second pregnancy trimester producing a direct damage of the brain of the fetus. The current available technology doesn't allow observing what is happening at cellular level since the human brain is not exposed to a direct analysis in that stage of the life in subjects at high risk of developing schizophrenia. **Methods.** In 1977 we began a direct electron microscopic research of the brain of fetuses at high risk from schizophrenic mothers in order to finding differences at cellular level in relation to controls. **Results.** In these studies we have observed within the nuclei of neurons the presence of complete and incomplete viral particles that reacted in positive form with antibodies to herpes simplex hominis type I [HSV1] virus, and mitochondria alterations. **Conclusion.** The importance of these findings can have practical applications in the prevention of the illness keeping in mind its direct relation to the aetiology and physiopathology of schizophrenia. A study of amniotic fluid cells in women at risk of having a schizophrenic offspring is considered. Of being observed the same alterations that those observed previously in the cells of the brain of the studied foetuses, it would intend to these women in risk of having a schizophrenia descendant, previous information of the results, the voluntary medical interruption of the pregnancy or an early anti HSV1 viral treatment as preventive measure of the later development of the illness.

Biography:

Segundo Mesa Castillo. As Specialist in Neurology, he worked for 10 years in the Institute of Neurology of Havana, Cuba. He has worked in Electron Microscopic Studies on Schizophrenia for 32 years. He was awarded with the International Price of the Stanley Foundation Award Program and for the Professional Committee to work as a fellowship position in the Laboratory of the Central Nervous System Studies, National Institute of Neurological Diseases and Stroke under Dr. Joseph Gibbs for a period of 6 months, National Institute of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, Washington D.C. USA, June 5, 1990.

Neurovascular Coupling in patients with ischemic stroke

Xiuyun Liu, PhD^{1*}; Liping Liu, PhD²; Xiao Hu, PhD¹

¹Department of Physiological Nursing, University of California, San Francisco, USA

²Neurointensive Care Unit, Department of Neurology, Beijing Tiantan Hospital, Beijing, China

Email: liuxiuyun1@gmail.com

Abstract:

Background : Neurovascular coupling enables adaptation of cerebral blood flow (CBF) to support neuronal activity. Modern techniques enable the simultaneous recording of neuronal activities and hemodynamic parameters. However, the neurovascular coupling mechanism remains understudied. In this study, we applied a phase-amplitude cross-frequency coupling (PAC) algorithm to investigate multimodal neuro signals including surface electroencephalogram (EEG) and CBF from transcranial Doppler ultrasonography (TCD). We also investigated the causal relationship between EEG and CBF with using Granger causality (GC) analysis.

Methods : Twenty simultaneous recordings of EEG and TCD cerebral blood flow velocity (CBFV) from 17 acute ischemic stroke patients admitted to the Neurointensive Care Unit, Tiantan Hospital, Capital Medical University (Beijing, China) were studied. Each patient had simultaneous, continuous monitoring of EEG and bilateral CBFV in either the middle cerebral arteries (MCA) or posterior cerebral arteries (PCA). PAC was calculated between the phase of CBFV in frequency bands (0–0.05 and 0.05–0.15 Hz) and the EEG amplitude in five bands (δ , θ , α , β , γ). The global PAC was calculated as the sum of all PACs across the six EEG channels and five EEG bands for each patient. The hemispherical asymmetry of cross-frequency coupling (CFC) was calculated as the difference between left and right PAC. GC analysis was carried out to investigate causal interactions between slow waves of FV (frequency band: 0.006 - 0.4 Hz) and the amplitude of EEG in five frequency bands. Mean GC index across EEG frequency bands was calculated to estimate the causal relationship between EEG and CBFV and then correlated with NIH Stroke Scale (NIHSS) at admission/discharge and the modified Rankin Scale (mRS, favorable outcome when mRS \leq 2) at discharge.

Results : The PAC between CBFV and EEG was significantly higher in β and γ bands than in the other three bands. Occipital region (P3-O1 and P4-O2 channels) showed stronger PAC than the other regions. The deceased group tended to have smaller global PAC than the survival group (the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve [AUROC] was 0.81, $p = 0.57$). The unfavorable outcome group showed smaller global PAC than the favorable group (AUROC = 0.65, $p = 0.23$). The PAC asymmetry between the two brain hemispheres correlates with the degree of stenosis in stroke patients ($p = 0.01$).

Granger analysis identified a causal relationship from EEG \rightarrow FV, indicating past EEG contained information that predicted CBFV. The NIHSS negatively correlates with mean GC index value, which means a stronger causality between EEG and FV exists in patients who are less severely affected. No significant difference in GC index exists between patients with favorable and unfavorable outcomes ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion : We showed that CBFV interacts with EEG in β and γ bands through a phase-amplitude CFC relationship, with the strongest PAC found in the occipital region and that the degree of hemispherical asymmetry of CFC correlates with the degree of stenosis. A G-causality causal relationship from EEG \rightarrow CBFV may exist in patients with ischemic stroke. The strength of G-causality may be related to stroke severity at discharge.

Key Words:

Neurovascular Coupling, Stroke,

Figure 1: (A) Mean phase-amplitude cross-frequency coupling (PAC) between CBFV (0–0.05 Hz) and EEG of six channels in five frequency bands (δ , θ , α , β , γ) of the 16 patients. (B) Statistical comparison of mean PAC between CBFV (0–0.05 Hz) and EEG in the 5 frequency bands (δ , θ , α , β , γ). (C) Mean PAC between CBFV (0.05–0.15 Hz) and EEG of six channels in five frequency bands of the 16 patients. (D) Statistical comparison of mean PAC between CBFV (0.05–0.15 Hz) and EEG in the 5 frequency bands.)

Endoscopic removal of growth hormone secreting pituitary tumor- My experiences of twelve cases

Dr. Md. Atikur Rahman

Associate Professor Department Neurosurgery Bangbandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University, Shahbag, Dhaka

Email: atiquessmc@yahoo.com

Abstract:

The use of endoscope for the management of pituitary adenoma is not new. The better magnification and illumination provided by the endoscope gives better outcome than microscopic pituitary surgery. The purpose of the study to find outcome of growth hormone secreting pituitary adenoma. I did twelve cases of pituitary adenoma last three years. All patients presented to me features of acromegaly with headache and visual disturbances and hormone profile shows growth hormone above normal level. I prepared all patients for surgery by purely endoscopic removal. After surgery growth hormone became normal of 10 cases and one became half of initial level and patient need re surgery by transcranial approaches and one is loss of follow up. I used fat graft, fascia lata, vascularized pedicle flap, biological glow for repair of seller floor. No mortality and no CSF leak in reported cases.

Keywords:

Growth Hormone, Adenoma. Pituitary